

The Drill of Parental Intervention on Children's Television Watching in Kaffa Zone Bonga Town

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Abstract:- The study's main goal was to look into children's television-watching habits, and drills used by parents to intervene their children's television watching. It also examines the link between parental intervention drills and Bonga town's socioeconomic condition. The study was conducted using a survey research design. The information was gathered from two schools: one governmental and the other a private school. The study enlisted 200 parents. Questionnaires were used to acquire data. Descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were obtained using SPSS 26. Chi-square tests were used to investigate the association between parental television viewing habits and children's television viewing habits. Similarly, descriptive statistics were employed to investigate the presence and lack of parental television intervention, yielding the finding that more than half of the participants use television intervention strategies, while the remainder do not monitor their children's television viewing habits. This study confirmed that, a strong association observed between parental television viewing hours and children's school day and weekend viewing hours. Finally, the current research looked at the practice of parental television intervention in relation to socioeconomic level. There was a strong link between parental television intervention and monthly household income. The findings revealed, parents should begin paying attention to their children's television watching habits and use effective television intervention tactics to reduce television's detrimental impact.

Keywords:- Children, Drill, Intervention, Parent and Television.

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to its extensive use and availability, television, as a kind of media, plays a significant influence in the lives of youngsters. Television is an important element of most families' activities, and it continues to consume the majority of young people's spare time (Vittrup, 2009). Since it initially aired in every country's living rooms in the mid-twentieth century, observers have expressed recurring concerns about the influence it has on viewers, particularly youngsters.

Study of the media use of children aged 0 to 6 finds that these very young children live in media-saturated environment and spend two hours daily in front of a screen on average. (Vandewater Park, Huang, & Wartella, 2005) Watching habits typically increase throughout elementary school years and decreases during high school years. The years right before and after adolescence are the most

opportune times to shape television watching habits. (Shanthy, Kanniammal, Jaideep & Valli, 2017).

Research findings indicate several negative effects of television watching that relate to an increased amount of watching as well as exposure to inappropriate television content. According to Gentile and Walsh (2002), some of the mentioned effects include "increased aggression, increased obesity, lowered school performance and prevalence of symptoms of psychological trauma." Another evidence has begun to link media exposure and mental, including self-esteem, depression, poorer mental health, sleeping problem and anxiety in both children and adults. (Kavitha, 2006).

Daniel, Aletha, Kelly, Schmitt, John & Reed, (2001) stated that, Television watching is related to improved creative ability, better school readiness and higher ambition. This research also assessed that time spent in front of the television influences children's emotional and cognitive development.

Huesmann and Miller (1994) proposed that television content contributes to children's cognitive scripts: learned patterns of action that lead to expectations about others, one's own behavior, consequences of that behavior, and acceptable forms of social problem solving. Repeated watching leads children to retrieve, rehearse, solidify, and expand existing scripts, resulting in cumulative long-term effects. The same principles can be applied to cognitive and academic content. The same research suggests that electronic media might have an effect on attention skills. Television especially when viewed by children younger than age two, may have a negative effect on attention development though the evidence is relatively weak.

Considering the fact that a large number of children are granted easy access to the use of television with all its advantages and potential detrimental effects it is important to question parental awareness towards television usage, level of involvement to influence children's television watching habit, socio economic status of the parents and parental understanding and attitude of the threat posed by the unsupervised exposure of inappropriate content. (Heather, et al. 2008).

Parents play significant role in their child's television. Parental intervention refers to the interaction that parents have with their children about their media use. (Pavleen & Manisha, 2014).

Parental intervention of children's media exposure involves any of three different behaviors that occur before during and after media use and are distinct from others more and general aspects of parents- child interactions such as overall parental monitoring of the teenagers' leisure time. (Nathanson, 2001)

According to Nathanson (1999) parental intervention is conceptualized as a three-dimensional construct. Although a variety of labels has been used through the years to describe subtypes of mediation, three different strategies of intervention which include active mediation, restrictive mediation, and co-Watching intervention to regulate the television contents children are exposed.

Parents using "restrictive" strategies prohibit Watching of specific television contents whereas those that use "active" intervention strategies focus on discussing or explaining the content of television to their children. Co-Watching intervention occurs when parents watch television with their children without discussing television use or content. (Warren, 2005).

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

It seems that recently; in Ethiopia almost, the entire household's own television with free paid channels. This television availability has made children to spend most of their time on watching television next to their school time. Children are mostly exposed to adult contents that are not specifically designed for them. If we consider the domestic channels available in the country, it is evident that the shortage of age appropriate children's program in the country has aggravated children's exposure to adult television contents. It is observed in many homes of Bonga that children equally watch all kinds of programs with their parents or guardians with no or little restriction. At a time when the level of awareness in most homes on the effect of television contents are not yet fully realized, children's exposure to inappropriate television content is becoming detrimental to their development as a whole and its cumulative effect is yet to be seen.

Watching are associated with negative effects on sleep, attention, interpersonal relationships, and aggression, sexual behavior, substance use, disordered eating and academic difficulties. Families might have different norms for media use. Some families might have strict rules about media, while other families pay little attention to what or how much media kids consume. In Bonga, parents in different schools are worrying about the effects of unnecessary television watching habit on their children. Researchers found out that media exposure influences cognitive development and Academic achievement. (Heather, et al. 2008) This same research suggests that electronic media might have an effect on attention skills.

Another Finding suggests that, the relationship between television watching and children's development is complex. First, the likely effects of television may depend on children's individual characteristics, family and social context. Second, the features of television such as content and editing pace and the type of exposure (foreground and

background) may affect outcomes. Specifically watching high quality educational content during preschool years improves children's basic academic skills and predicts subsequent positive advantage. (Jolin & Miller, 2017).

This time, parents must/should act as filters and monitor the influences of the other intervention agents that participate in children's everyday lives, including television, especially when television's messages and parent's criteria differ. (Teresa, 2013) Television's ability to affect children cannot be underestimated due to the intense and suggestive ways with which television communicates its messages to children. Other research on parental television monitoring indicates that parents can reduce the negative effects of media exposure on children and contribute to the development of its positive effect by actively involving in giving guidance in their children's Watching (Nathanson, 2001). Parents really need intervention strategies to control their children television watching habits. Parental intervention has been described as one of the most effective ways in managing television's influence on children. (Kelly, 2009).

Supporting parents in the difficult task of monitoring media exposure is needed to increase parents' self-efficiency. (Tina, 2004) Recently, most parents are seen being engaged in fulfilling basic necessities for their families and making money so they are unable to guide and monitor their children as it should be, due to this problem, media especially television is taking advantage of socializing and leading children. So, this research will investigate the presence of parental intervention in Bonga. Moreover, the study aimed to identify the type of intervention strategy parents used most. As a result, parents will have an insight of some effective intervention strategies in order to monitor their children's television watching habit. In addition, the study also set out to explore the contribution of socio-economic status on the drill of parental television intervention.

As a result, doing research in Bonga town on the Drill of Parental Intervention on Children's Television Watching will help us better understand the Drill of Parental Intervention on Children's Television Watching. As a result, the research topics addressed in this study are as follows:

- How is the television watching habit of children in Bonga town?
- Do parents intervene their children's television Watching?
- What type of intervention strategies, do parents follow in order to regulate effects of television on their children?
- Is the drill of parental intervention different across children's television watching habit and socio-economic status of the family?

III. METHODS

Descriptive survey design was used to conduct this investigation. According to Frey & Cissan (2009) Survey method seeks to ascertain the beliefs, attitudes, values or behaviors of a population of interest from a sample of respondents selected from that population. Survey method will also allow gathering data from wider sample and enabling generalization to population.

Hence, the study was conducted in Bonga town and the study site incorporates both the government and private schools (Sheta 03 elementary school and Birhan elementary school) as well as the schools had the total of 1502 students from grade 5 up to grade 8. The sample size was calculated using Krejcie and Morgan’s (1970) formula was consulted. The formula is:

$$S = \frac{X_2NP(1 - P)}{d^2(N - 1) + x^2P(1 - P)}$$

Where: s = required sample size; X2 = the table value of chi-square for 1 degree of freedom at the Desired confidence level (3.841); N = the population size (580 in this case); P = the population proportion (assumed to be .50 since this would provide the maximum sample size); and d =

the degree of accuracy expressed as a proportion (.05). Using this formula, the equivalent sample size for 580 population sizes is 584. Once sampling frame of the population and sample size identified, researcher follows cluster sampling technique where each section are assumed to be cluster from which random sections are selected. The existence of a homogeneous group in terms of the variables the researcher is interested in justifies the use of cluster sampling. Following the identification of clusters, the researcher used a simple random procedure to select sections from each grade, and all students’ parents were included as participants. Assume that the sample includes both genders and all grades.

After the data was obtained, it was analyzed using a variety of statistical tools. Apart from methodically documenting the variables of interest, analysis is carried out between them with the goal of finding their empirical relationship. Inferential statistics, such as chi-square tests, were used to create percentage tables and graphs. The following assumptions apply to Chi square: first, the two variables should be measured on an ordinal and nominal level. The second assumption is two variables should consist of two or more categorical, independent groups. (Robert, 2009).

IV. RESULT

Demographic characteristics	N	Percent
Gender (parents) Female	114	56.5%
Male	86	43.5%
Gender (Children) Female	107	53%
Male	98	47%
Marital status Unmarried	126	5%
Married	134	66.5%
Divorced	24	12.5%
Widowed	20	10.5%
Separated	12	6.5%
Education Can write and read	126	5%
Primary Education	14	7.5%
Secondary school	26	13.0%
Certificate	22	11.0%
College diploma	60	29.0%
1st degree and above	66	33%
Income Less than 5,000 birr	90	44.5%
5,000 birrs – 10,000 birrs	105	5.5%
10,000 birrs – 15,000 birrs	21	10.5%
15,000-birr -20,000 birr	45	22.5%
Above 20,000-birr	34	17%

Table 1: Socio demographic characteristics of respondents (N = 200)

According to the above table, among the 107 (53 percent) female and 98 (47 percent) male students picked, 85 (42.5%) were fathers and 115 (57.5%) were mothers. Furthermore, the chart shows that 66.5 percent of the respondents were married, whereas 19 percent were widowed. According to the data, 12 (6.5 percent) of the respondents only knew how to read and write, while 26 (13 percent) had completed high school (Grades 9-12) and 13 (6.5 percent) had completed primary school (Grade 1-8).

Respondents with a bachelor's degree or more make up 66 percent of the total, while those with a diploma make up 60 percent (29 percent).

According to the report, 45.5 percent of respondents have a monthly income of less than 5,000 ETB. Furthermore, 22.5 percent of respondents have an average monthly salary of 15,000 – 20,000 ETB, with 17 percent earning more than 20,000 ETB.

Obtaining background information on television access in the house is a critical component of the study, since it indicates the level of television exposure experienced by

children. As a result, belowgraph illustrates television ownership in the evaluated families.

According to the graph above, 196 (198 percent) of the studied residences have access to television, while only 4 (2 percent) do not.

A number of questions were asked to assess respondents' television viewing habits, including viewing time and show preference. The study's findings in connection to parental Watching Hours are depicted in the graph below.

The graph above depicts the distribution of parents based on the number of hours they spend watching television each day. 98 respondents (48.5 percent) stated they watch 1hr – 1:30 minutes of television per day,

followed by 87 respondents (43.5 percent) who watch 1hr:30 min – 2:00 hours of television per day. Furthermore, ten percent of respondents (5%) watch television for 30 minutes to an hour, while four percent (2%) watch television

for less than 30 minutes, and only one percent (0.5%) does not watch television at all.

Preferred television program	N	%
News	185	82.5%
Comedy	84	42%
Documentary	42	21%
Action film	47	23.5%
Family film	92	46.0%
Horror film	22	11%
Police program	37	18.5%
Reality show	45	22.5%
Sport	93	46.5%
Drama	157	78.5%
Music	130	65%

As shown in the table above, the most popular television programs are news 185 (82.5%), comedy 84 (42%), documentary 42 (21%), action film 47 (23.5%), family film 92 (46.5%), horror film 22 (11%), police program 37 (11%), reality show 45 (22.5%), sport 93 (46.5%), drama 157 (78.5%), and finally music 130 (65%).

Parents reported on their children's viewing habits in terms of time spent watching, program selection, and program preference. Children's television viewing hours on school days and weekends, as reported by their parents, are depicted in graphs 3 and 4.

Figure 3 Children Television Viewing Hours on School Days

As seen in the graph above, 5 (2.5%) of children watch television for more than two hours on school days. 55 (27%) of children watch one to two hours and a half of television. Furthermore, the graph shows that 18 (9%) of respondents said their children watch television for one and

a half to two hours during school days, while 46 (23%) said their children watch television for less than half an hour. Finally, the graph shows that 28 percent of children (14 percent) do not watch television throughout the school day.

Figure 4. Children television viewing Hours on weekend days

On days when they are sick, 51 (25.5%) of children watch television for more than two hours, as seen in the graph. 60 percent of youngsters (or 30 percent) watch 1 hour to 1:30 minutes of television. In addition, the graph shows that on weaker days, 55 (27%) of respondents say their children watch television for one hour and a half to two hours, while 4 (2%) say they watch television for less than half an hour. Finally, the graph reveals that on days when they are sick, 4 (2%) of children do not watch television.

Parents were asked to provide information about their children's favorite TV programs. According to the study, 185 (92.5%) of respondents indicated their children prefer to watch kids shows, while 155 (77%) prefer cartoon shows, 133 (66.5%) drama, and 122 (61%) instructional shows. Wrestling is also a popular sport in the United States, according to the report.

Preferred television program	N	Percentage (%)
Cartoon film	155	77.5%
Kana	133	66.5%
Kids program	185	92.5%
Educational	122	61%
Riesling	30	15%
Sport	48	24%
Horror	19	9.5%

Table 3: Children’s television program in order of preference. (N = 200)

The researchers also wanted to discover if there was a link between parental and kid television viewing hours. Tables 4 and 5 show a cross-tabulation of parental and child television viewing time in hours.

Parental Television Watching		None	< 30min	30min-1h	1hr-1:30mi	1:30 mi-2hr	Total	Df	X2
Children school day Watching	None	0	1	2	18	7	25	20	33.696
	Less than 30 min	0	0	5	25	16	46		
	30 min-1hr	1	0	2	25	20	48		
	1hr-1:30min	0	2	1	24	28	55		
	1:30 min-2:00hr	0	0	0	4	14	18		
	Over 2 hours	0	1	0	2	2	5		
	Total	1	4	10	98	87	200		

Table 4: Cross tabulation of Parental Television Watching Hours and Children School Day Television Watching Hours)

	None	< 30min	30min-1h	1hr-1:30min	1:30 min-2hr	Total	Df	X2	P
None	0	0	0	2	0	2	20	215.282	0.000
Less than 30 min	0	3	0	1	0	4			
30 min-1hr	0	0	3	7	5	15			
1hr-1:30min	1	0	2	73	11	87			
1:30min-2:00	0	1	0	10	57	68			
Over 2 hours	0	0	1	9	13	23			
Total	1	4	6	102	87	200			

Table 5: Cross tabulation of Parental Television Watching Hours. and Children Weekend Television Watching Hours.)

The chi square result shows that there is an association between parental Watching hours and children’s school day Watching hours at [X2= 33.69, df= 20, p< 0.05] also the chi square showed there is also an association between parental Watching hours and children weekend Watching hours at [X2 = 215.282, df = 24, p < 0.05].

Simple Bar Count of Parental opinions on how much inappropriate content (violence, sexual content, offensive language) does television have.

The above bar graph displays for parental opinion on how much inappropriate content (violence, sexual content,offensive language) does television have

It can be seen from bar graph 5 that 71(35.5%) believe that, television has less influence on their children’s behavior. Moreover, 14 (7%) of the respondents consider television as having no influence on children’s behavior. The graph also revealed that, slightly more than half of the respondents 115 (57.5%) believed that television has more influence on children’s behavior.

In order to have a better understanding of parental awareness, parental recognition of the occurrence of inappropriate content on television was also assessed. According to the data, 111 (55.5%) of parents believe there is a lot of unsuitable television content within children’s reach, while more than half of 66 (33%) of respondents believe the incidence of improper television content is moderate. Finally, the graph reveals that 23 (11.5%) of respondents believe there is a small quantity of unsuitable television content on television transitions.

The second research topic was whether or not parents moderate their children’s television viewing. They were invited to convey their feelings about their television mediation drill. The results revealed that 138 (63.8 percent) of the 200 samples returned said they moderate their children’s television viewing through various mechanisms, while 62 (30.7 percent) said they either don’t monitor their children’s television viewing at all or let them watch everything the family watches.

The third research question looked into which parental intervention tactics were most commonly adopted by parents. The Television Intervention Scale was used to do this. The 15-item scale included a variety of intervention items that were divided into three 5-item mediation subscales: active mediation, restricted intervention, and co-Watching intervention, allowing researchers to analyze the degree and type of parental intervention. The minimum and maximum scores for each sub-scale were five and twenty, respectively.

By comparing each household’s sum of scores in each intervention method, the frequency with which parents used each intervention style was determined. The intervention technique that received the highest score was chosen as the one that would be practiced the most. However, because they did not identify which intervention approach they drill in their homes, 16 (8%) of families who reported using more than one intervention strategy were excluded from the study.

Intervention strategies	N	%
Active mediation	55	25.5%
Restriction mediation	53	25.5%
Co-Watching mediation	92	43%

Table 6 Frequency of Parental Television Intervention Stratagems (N=200)

The most common intervention strategy used by parents is co-Watching, followed by active and restrictive mediation, as indicated in Table. Because equal samples were taken from government and private schools, the findings revealed that government schools primarily drill co-Watching intervention, followed by restrictive and active

interventions, while private school parents reported that active intervention, restrictive intervention, and co-Watching intervention were all equally drilled. The fourth research question investigated if parental intervention drills differed depending on a child’s television viewing habits and the family’s socioeconomic position.

	Active	Restrictive	Co-Watching	Df	X2	P
<5000ETB (Government School)	9	12	83	12	31.722	0.002
>5000ETB (Private School)	16	51	72			

Table 7: Chi – tests on parental television intervention and monthly household income.

The Chi-square test was conducted to see if there was a link with parental television intervention drills and their household's monthly income. A significant link between the two variables was found using the chi-square test, with $X^2 = 31.772$, $df = 12$, and $p = .002$. The fact that there was a substantial relationship between these variables shows that parental television intervention varies according to household income.

V. DISCUSSION

The goal of this study was to look at children's television watching habits, as well as to examine the presence and practice of parental television intervention and to learn about the different styles of intervention employed by parents. Furthermore, the study sought to determine whether socioeconomic class had any bearing on parental television mediation drills.

According to the literature evaluation, television is an important element of family life that continues to consume the majority of young people's spare time (Vittrup, 2009). Because of its extensive use and availability, television, as one kind of media, plays a significant influence in the lives of children. According to a recent study, 99.5 percent of people own a television. This can be beneficial in terms of expanding knowledge and broadening experiences, or it can be a breeding ground for a variety of unintended behavioral impacts on youngsters that are yet to manifest. While the good impacts of this type of exposure on children's behavior are encouraged, the negative consequences of this type of exposure on children's behavior must be regulated, particularly in homes with children. The number of hours spent watching television by youngsters on school days and weekends was disclosed in this study.

According to parents, 5 (2.5%) of youngsters watch television for more than two hours every day throughout the school day. 55 (27%) of children watch television for one to two hours and a half hour. Furthermore, the graph shows that 18 (9%) of respondents said their children watch television for one and a half to two hours during school days, while 46 (23%) said their children watch television for less than half an hour. Finally, the graph shows that 28 percent of children (14 percent) do not watch television throughout the school day.

According to the relevant literature, which is a study of the media use of children aged 5 to 10, these young children live in a media-saturated environment and spend an average of two hours per day in front of a screen. (Van dewater and colleagues, 2005).

Furthermore, a recent study found that 51 (25.5%) of children watch television for more than two hours on most

days. 60 (30%) of children watch 1hr – 1:30min of television. Furthermore, the poll found that 55 (27%) of respondents said their children watch television for one hour and a half to two hours on weakened days, while 4 (2%) said their children watch television for less than half an hour. Finally, the study reveals that 4 (2%) of children do not watch television on days when they are sick. During elementary school, students' viewing habits tend to increase, and during high school, they tend to decrease. The years leading up to and following puberty are the best for shaping television viewing habits. (2017, Shanthi et al.)

Previous studies have shown that a parent's watching habits influence their children's watching habits (Sandstig et al., 2013). In keeping with the literature, the current study found a link between parental television viewing hours and children's viewing hours throughout the school day and on weekends. The chi square result reveals that parental Watching hours and children's school day Watching hours have a very strong relationship. The same can be said for parental viewing hours and children's weekend viewing hours.

The purpose of the study was to see if parents use any kind of monitoring system to keep track on their children's television viewing habits. According to the findings of this study, 138 (63.8 percent) of parents report that they mediate their children's television viewing through various mechanisms, while 62 (30.7 percent) report that they either do not monitor their children's television viewing at all or allow them to watch whatever the rest of the family does. This means that slightly more than half of the parents in the poll said they supervise their children's television viewing habits using various methods, while 30.7 percent said they either let their child watch anything they want with the family or have no monitoring strategy at all. The percentage difference between the two indicates that as much as there are parents who pro-actively monitor their children's television usage, there are also parents who are lenient to pay much attention to their children's television exposure. The intervention of parents has strong relationship with the recognition of the occurrence of inappropriate content on television.

Because of a lack of awareness of the necessity of filtering television content and of the potential detrimental impacts of television, parents who are indulgent in paying close attention to their children's television exposure. Even though the study revealed that parents are aware of unsuitable television content, they chose to expose their children to adult things that are not intended for them. In fact, one of the justifications for parents regulating their children's television viewing is that they are becoming more aware of improper content on television. As expected, I'm

keeping an eye on things. This contrasts with Rue's (1974) explanation of why parents fail to supervise their children when they watch television, which states that the failure could be due to an inability to enforce supervision or a positive attitude towards television in general as well as the difficulty to differentiate between contents that are detrimental and educational.

The fact that more than half of the parent's delegate program selection to their children is yet another sign of parental mediation in these households. To recapitulate, it is predicted that if parents can discern the magnitude of inappropriate information on television and understand the impact of television on their children's conduct, they will be able to effectively mediate. However, the outcome revealed the exact reverse. This could be due to a combination of luck and indifference.

Because parents know everything there is to know about the social environment, children must rely on their parents to help them comprehend themselves in it. As a result, parental involvement is commonly thought to be a parental intervention that can help prevent negative media effects. (Nathanson, 2001) (Nathanson, 2001) (Nathanson, 2001) In keeping with this, the study's third goal was to determine which type of intervention was most commonly employed by parents. According to the findings, co-Watching is the most common television intervention technique among the sampled parents, with (43 percent) of parents saying that they use it, followed by active (25.5 percent) and restrictive (25.5 percent) intervention styles.

This research suggests that parents are facilitating children's exposure to adult materials on television without taking into account the type of information that children should or should not be exposed to. This could be explained by parents' lack of knowledge of the severity of the impact of their children's exposure to such information. Co-Watching allows parents to turn the process of watching into a more constructive and educational discussion. Co-Watching can help children grasp children's programs, according to the same research. Children who watch educational programs are included in this category. Youngsters who are accompanied by their parents may gain a better understanding of the subject than children who are not accompanied by their parents. (Nathanson, 2001; Nathanson, 2002; Nathanson, 2002; Nathanson, 2002; However, most parents miss out on this chance and instead focus on the programs they are watching, often refusing to acknowledge the presence of youngsters.

The current study's findings demonstrated a substantial association between parental income and television intervention drill, implying that parental television intervention varies according to household income. The outcome also demonstrated the intervention drill in both public and private schools. This suggests that government school parents primarily practice co-Watching intervention, which is followed by restrictive and aggressive intervention tactics. Parents from private schools practice active intervention, restrictive intervention, and co-watching intervention strategies in equal measure. This meant that

most parents from private schools don't have time to spend with their children since they are so busy, so instead of sitting together and watching, they were able to freely talk with their children the positive and negative aspects of television. Parents who discuss television content with their children, according to Nathanson (2002) and Pavleen & Manisha (2014), boost their children's chances of understanding and learning from it. In addition, Pavleen and Manisha, 2014 discussed that active intervention alsodemonstrates deliberate comment and actively explaining the nature and selling intent of television content by parents.

In general, this agrees with findings from others such as Van dewater et al. (2005), who found that parents with a high socioeconomic position were more likely to have rules about television watching, which is one type of mediation. According to Vittrup (2009) and Warren (2005), households with a low socioeconomic status reported a higher degree of co-Watching than those with a higher socioeconomic status. This conclusion supports the current finding, as the study revealed that the average monthly income of parents who send their children to government schools is less than 5000 ETB, which is among the lowest in the country. More research is also needed to see what the effects of co-watching are in homes where it is so common.

VI. CONCLUSION

The study found that practically every household had a child who watches television. Furthermore, the findings confirm the common practice of parental television intervention in many families, despite the presence of all three intervention forms, and the study also revealed the prevalence of parental co-watching. The study also revealed the dangers that many youngsters face when they are raised in homes where television viewing is not regulated. The considerable association between parents' and children's viewing hours supports the notion that children are exposed to adult items that are not intended for them.

As more access to television and more television channels becomes available in homes, children's exposure to improper television programming will continue to rise. To safeguard children from unsuitable television content, it is critical to execute an effective intervention plan that teaches children how to be selective and identify television contents that are solely beneficial and educational.

Parents play an important role in controlling their children's television viewing habits and monitoring the influences of various socializing agents in their children's daily life, including television.

The study also shed light on how parental and children's television viewing habits, as well as access to both domestic and satellite television channels, providing a peek of the level of exposure easily available for youngsters.

The fact that all of the results were dependent on parents' self-reports is one of the study's shortcomings. Social desirability reactions are based on these types of responses. When asked about the employment of

intervention tactics, parents are more likely to respond according to what they believe is socially acceptable rather than what they truly understand and think.

Another weakness of the current study is that it did not look into other forms of media, such as online media. Future studies should go deeper into this topic. Furthermore, the study's researcher feels that content-specific studies might yield more tangible results in terms of parental intervention strategies. .

Furthermore, the study did not examine the level of parental worry about the effects of unsuitable television programming in depth. The study's most noteworthy contributions, however, were the revelations of parents' and children's television watching habits, as well as the drill and level of parental television mediation.

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS

The researcher makes the following recommendations based on the above-mentioned explanations of the primary results and conclusions.

- More than anything else, parents are instructed to pay attention to, be aware of, and be critical of their children.
- Television control systems, such as parental guidance devices on satellite transmitters, should be designed by innovators.
- Using diverse shows, panel discussions, and films, the media should provide targeted messages to enhance parental awareness.
- Administrators, experts, psychologists, practitioners, and social policymakers are encouraged to create an intervention project to retain our cultures and norms within the generation.
- Schools and teachers are advised to seriously teach advice and also warn students about
- selecting television contents.
- Finally, this study gave some implications for future research. First, future research should expand the scope of the present study (on different age groups, on online media, on mobile and computer usage and so on). Second, the future research should include children's report during survey. Third, the future research should conduct actual observation of parental and children's media usage.

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• Competing interest

The authors have declared that there are no contending welfares.

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